

QUIZ**LAST NAME: PA ALIEU****FIRST NAME: FOFANA****PROGRAM CODE: MBAIF****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following is, according to Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, the correct definition of in-text citation?**

- It is the citing a piece of work within the actual text itself.¹**
- It is the act of mentioning authors' names after writing.
- It is acknowledging those who support your writing.
- It is a list of all sources of information at the end of a research.

2. **Kate L. Turabian discussed about some reasons for citation, which of the following is not mentioned in this regard?**

- Giving credit to authors or sources
- Assure readers about accuracy of facts.
- To help readers follow or extend the research.

¹Laurent Cleenewerck and KabiruGulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2019), 6.

To demonstrate your writing skills.²

3. **Gulma and Cleenewerck in their identification of common errors in research papers, which of the following is not mentioned?**

- Do not use direct quotes.
- Avoid irrelevant information.
- Avoid inaccurate word or phrase.

Put your work aside for some time before editing.³

4. **Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma in their recognition on how to avoid plagiarism, which of the following is correct?**

- Include the authors name and source in the reference list.
- To properly cite the author(s) or source that has provided the information.⁴**
- To exactly copy the text of a source when paraphrasing then cites.
- To take permission from author(s) before using any information.

5. **Kate L. Turabian in her recommendation for the use of punctuations during parenthetical citation, which of the following is correct?**

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff., 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 5-11.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 6.

- Not to use punctuation mark between the author and the date.**⁵
 - Separate most elements with periods
 - Put punctuation between the author and the date.
 - Not to separate the date and the page number with a comma.
6. **Which of the following best defines reference list according to Gulma and Cleenewerck?**
- It is a list of all sources consulted during research.
 - It is a list of all sources cited in a work.**⁶
 - It is a list of sources used to write a research but not cited
 - It is a list of sources that an instructor or faculty recommend for a research.
7. **According to the European Commission, which of the following rule is correct for the use of English language?**
- Question mark is needed after a request and instruction.
 - Question mark can be used in indirect speech.
 - Question mark should not be closed up to the preceding word.

⁵ Turabian, 128.

⁶ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 59.

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 19.

- Do not use a question mark in indirect speech.**⁷⁸
8. **Paraphrasing according to Gulma and Cleenewerck can be defined as**
- Presenting another person's ideas in your own ideas.**⁹
- Using someone's ideas as express in the original text.
- Using another person's ideas without citing.
- Making best use of synonyms to replace someone's ideas in a research.
9. **Which of the following option is not mentioned by Cleenewerck and Gulma in their recognition of some rule of Thumb for writing papers?**
- Write clearly.
- Take the view you are discussing seriously.
- Do not plagiarize.
- Make best use of word power.**¹⁰
10. **Which of the following is not part of the usage of colons in the correct use of English Language, according to the European Commission?**
- Do not use colons at the end of headings.**¹¹
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⁸European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 19.

⁹Cleenewerck and Gulma, 56.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14-16

- Colon requires that the next word to start with capital.
- Use colons at the end of headings.
- Colon requires that the next word to start with capital.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. European Commission, 2011.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.